

Evaluation of the Efficacy of Several Plant-Based Insecticides and Aqueous Nano-Silica Formulations Against the Rust-Red Flour *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst.) Under Laboratory Conditions

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Abstract:

Laboratory studies were conducted to evaluate the effects of plant-based insecticides such as Tandexir and Balizin, hydrophilic nanosilica compounds in addition to biopesticides synergistic with nanocompounds to estimate the effects of rust-red flour beetle *Tribolium castaneum* the mortality percentage Efficacy was evaluated. The results showed the effectiveness of tundexir insecticide with a statistically significant difference of up to 75% in obtaining higher mortality rate, compared to Balizin which obtained a rate of 63.61%. Furthermore, the results showed that 4 ml liter⁻¹ dose of Tandexir was more effective than Balizin with a statistical difference after 5 days of treatment, resulting in mortality rates of 93.33% and 83.33%,

respectively. For both formulations, a dose of 4 ml litre⁻¹ was the most effective in obtaining mortality, and 100% was recorded after 7 days of treatment The results of the efficacy study of the nanosilica formulations showed that the 0.4 g liter⁻¹ dose showed high mortality at 100% after 7 days of treatment, when mortality time was obtained comparing dosages of 0.2 and 0.3 g liter⁻¹ in at the same time 76.66% and 83.33%. The results showed that using plant-based insecticides at a concentration of 2 ml per liter of water, together with 0.2 grams per liter of a water-friendly nanosilica compound, worked really well together. Tandexir exhibited superior performance in achieving higher mortality rates, reaching 100% after 7 days of treatment, with a mortality rate of 84.16%, compared to Balizin, which achieved a mortality rate of 96.66% at a concentration of 77.50%.

Keywords: *plant-based insecticides, biopesticides, Tribolium castaneum, products storage, nanocompounds.*

Introduction

The red flour beetle, *Tribolium castaneum* Herbst, belonging to the family Tenebrionidae, is one of the most important storage pests causing significant economic losses to stored grains and flour. Both larvae and adults live on infested grains and flour. The infected flour develops a distinctive odor due to the gases produced by the insects, which reduces the moisture content and cohesion of the dough (Al-Azzawi & Mohammed, 1983).

Feeding of the insect on wheat causes a decrease in its baking quality, directly affecting the bread and pastry industry. Additionally, insect residues in cereals and their products increase the concentration of urea, which is a toxic compound established to modify the chemical composition of cereals including this may affect industrial applications and cause difficulties in milling machine (Tripathi *et al.*, 2001).

The most important challenges that threaten the process of preserving the quality of grain and by-products during storage are storage of pests. Attacks by various pests such as insects, rodents, etc. lead to severe losses of grain and stored products during storage. These attacks impart a distinctive odor to the ingredients due to volatile compounds, especially benzoquinones as a result (Rees, 2004). Food waste contaminates grains and its processing, thus affecting its market value. These pests include the red rust beetle *Tribolium castaneum* and the confused flour beetle *Tribolium confusum*, both of which belong to the family Tenebrionidae and are classified Coleoptera. Most of these beetles feed on decaying plant matter, while some attack inventories (Al-Iraqi & Ma'an, 2007).

The researchers found that the use of pesticides to control pest storage has caused a number of problems over time, including the emergence of pesticide-resistant organisms and drugs this accumulation in the environment, thereby contaminating human food and poisoning animals. This led researchers to search for alternative strategies to control insect pest storage, with the aim of promoting the concept of integrated pest management (IPM) and strategies environmentally friendly will be used to reduce the economic losses affecting rice and its by-products due to these insect pests (Mohammed *et al.*, 2019).

Pesticides from plants have been used as alternatives to chemicals, are non-toxic to many humans and animals, but have lethal effects and inhibit pests such as flour mildew. Humans use certain plants have long been used as repellents for harmful insects that attack stored products (Dawood *et al.*, 2009). Recently, nanocompounds have also been employed as safe alternatives within the framework of integrated pest management due to their high effectiveness and non-toxicity to humans (Al-Taie, 2018). Nanocompounds and plant-based pesticides are considered insect feeding deterrents, repellents, and growth inhibitors against various types of stored insect pests (Mohammed & Aswd, 2019).

Based on the information provided, the aim of this research is to biologically evaluate the efficacy of some plant-based pesticides, Tundexir and Balizin, in combination with hydrophilic nanosilica, and their synergistic effect on the Rust-red flour beetle *Tribolium castaneum*.

Materials and Methods

Collecting, Diagnosing, and Rearing Rust-Red Flour Beetles *T. castaneum*

Red flour beetles *T. castaneum* were obtained from samples of infested flour sourced from the insect laboratory at the Department of Plant Protection, College of Agriculture, University of Karbala. These samples had been previously diagnosed by Assistant Professor Dr. Sinaa Muslim Abd. 250 grams of healthy flour were placed in sterilized glass bottles with dimensions of (5×10) cm. Before offering the flour to the adult insects, it was placed in the freezer at a temperature of 5-7°C below zero for 24 hours to eliminate any potential insect infestation (Al-Jubawi, 2014). After that, more than 20 pairs of adult insects were released from each bottle for the purpose of egg laying. Then, the bottle mouths were covered with a piece of muslin cloth for ventilation and secured with rubber bands to prevent the insects from escaping. The bottles were then placed in an incubator at a temperature of $28 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and a relative humidity of $70 \pm 5\%$. Continuous colony renewal was ensured after each generation to obtain different ages of the insects for experimental purposes.

Plant-Origin Pesticides and Hydrophilic Nanosilica Compound

The plant-origin pesticides Tundexir and Balizin were provided by the distributing company, Planta Agroservice. As for the hydrophilic nanosilica compound (SNPs), it was obtained from Al-Bashir Laboratory Supplies and Medical Equipment Office, as shown in Table (1). The nanosilica was in the form of a white powder with particle size less than 5 microns and purity of 99.9%. This material was provided in a plastic package containing 10 grams and received as a

nanopowder with particle size less than 100 nanometers.

Table 1. Companies Producing Plant-Based Pesticides and Water-Lovable Silica Nanomaterials

Commercial Name	Chemical Group	Manufacturer
Palizin 65%SL	Coconut oil soap	Kimiasabzavar – Iran
Tondexir 80%EC	Garlic and red pepper extract	Kimiasabzavar – Iran
Nano-silica oxide	Hydrophilic nanocompound	US Research Nanomaterials

Laboratory Biological Evaluation of Plant-Origin Pesticides and Nanocompound

Newly emerged adults (both males and females) from the insect colony were distributed on plastic Petri dishes with dimensions of (16×9) cm. Each dish contained 5 grams of a mixture of food material at three replicates (each replicate containing 10 insects) for each concentration used. After calibrating the sprayer, three concentrations of the plant-origin pesticides Tundexir and Balizin were used: 2, 3, and 4 ml per liter of water, as well as three concentrations of the hydrophilic nanosilica compound: 0.2, 0.3, and 0.4 grams per liter of water. Additionally, a control treatment sprayed with water only was included. The Petri dishes were placed in an incubator at a suitable temperature for insect growth, 28 ± 2°C, and a relative humidity of 70 ± 5%. The dishes were examined after 1, 3, 5, and 7 days, and the numbers of dead insects were

recorded. As for the synergistic biological evaluation treatment between the concentration of 2 ml liter⁻¹ for both pesticides and a concentration of 0.2 grams for the nanocompound, it was conducted under the same steps and conditions mentioned above.

Statistical Analysis

The data of the study were statistically analyzed using the Completely Randomized Design (CRD) and a factorial experiment of 3*15 for each age stage. Only one stage of each age was tested. The significance was determined at the least significant difference (L.S.D) level with a probability of (P ≤ 0.05) to indicate the significance of the results (Al-Rawi & Khalf Allah, 2000). The results were analyzed using the statistical analysis program GenStat (2009). The percentage mortality was corrected according to the Abbot equation (1925).

$$\text{Corrected Mortality Rate (\%)} = \frac{\text{Mortality Rate in Treatment} - \text{Mortality Rate in Control Treatment}}{(100 - \text{Mortality Rate in Control Treatment})} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Results and Discussion

Laboratory Biological Evaluation of the Plant-Origin Pesticides Tundexir and Balizin on the Mortality Rate of Adult Rust-Red Flour Beetles *T. castaneum*

The results of Table 2 showed that the botanical insecticides Tundexir and Balizin exhibited significant differences in efficacy. Tundexir showed a higher mortality rate, reaching 75%, compared to balizine, which achieved a mortality

rate of 63.61%. Furthermore, tundexir at a concentration of 4 ml litre⁻¹ was more effective than balizin after 5 days of treatment, and the highest mortality rate was due to the 4 ml litre⁻¹ concentration of both formulations, despite mortality rates of 93.33% and 83.33%, respectively, in any case. which reached 100% after 7 days of treatment.

Table 2. Effect of Botanical Extract on Percentage Mortality of Adult *T. castaneum* Adult

Extract	Concentration ml L ⁻¹	The percentage of mortality after different treatment periods (Days)				Mean extract
		1	3	5	7	
Balizin	2	36.66	46.66	56.66	70.00	63.61
	3	46.66	53.33	73.33	90.00	
	4	50.00	56.66	83.33	100.00	
Tundexir	2	43.33	60.00	73.33	86.66	75.00
	3	53.33	66.66	86.66	96.66	
	4	66.66	73.33	93.33	100.00	
Control		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mean time		32.96	39.63	51.85	60.37	
Mean Conc.		3		4		
		39.44		47.50		51.66
LSD 0.05		Extract = 3.13 Conc. = 3.13 Time = 3.61 • Interaction= 10.85				

Superiority of Tandexir in achieving high mortality rates of adult insects compared to other plant-based insecticides. The effectiveness of Tandexir has been found to be due to the presence of secondary metabolites, e.g alkaloid compounds found in black pepper plants of piperine. Al-Quraishi (2001) found that the alcoholic extract of black pepper seeds achieved a mortality rate of 89.5% against adult *Tetranychus turkestanii* mites at a concentration of 1000 ppm. The effectiveness of pesticides is attributed to their content of potent volatile oils and compounds that have the ability to penetrate and spread among the insect's tissues in a manner resembling the action of contact pesticides. These chemical compounds penetrate the insect's cuticle through the thin regions of its body, causing paralysis and ultimately death (Afifi, 2002). Plant-origin pesticides contain toxic substances and alkaloid compounds or active compounds that prevent feeding, leading

to the death of insects. Additionally, plant-origin pesticides enter through the respiratory openings, affecting the nervous and digestive systems (Romeilah *et al.*, 2010).

Evaluation of the Efficacy of Hydrophilic Nanosilica in Mortality of *T. castaneum* Adult Rust Red Flour Beetle

In Table (3), the effect of different concentrations (0.2, 0.3, 0.4 ml liter⁻¹) of hydrophilic nanosilica on the mortality rate of adult red flour beetles was examined over varying time periods. The results of the statistical analysis revealed significant differences among the treatments. In particular, 0.4 ml liter⁻¹ dose showed the highest mortality rate, reaching 100% after 7 days of treatment, with a mortality rate of 78.33% compared to 0.2 and 0.3 ml liter⁻¹ doses, resulting in 76.66 at same period, respectively %, the mortality rate was 83.33%.

Table 3. Effect of Water-Friendly Nanosilica on the Mortality Rate of Adult *T. castaneum*

Concentration g L ⁻¹	The percentage of mortality after different treatment periods (Days)				Mortality rate (%)
	1	3	5	7	
0.2	50.00	56.66	66.66	76.66	62.50
0.3	56.66	63.33	76.66	83.33	70.00
0.4	60.00	70.00	83.33	100.00	78.33
Control	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mean time	41.66	47.50	56.66	65.00	
L.S.D 0.05	Conc. = 5.36 Time = 5.36 Interaction= 10.736				

The smaller the size of the nanoparticles, the greater the toxicity, according to Vaiyas *et al.* (2009). Kavallieratos *et al.* (2018) noted that the high effectiveness of silica nanoparticles is attributed to the small size of the compound particles. The variation in the effectiveness of the nanomaterial is attributed to differences in active components and depends on their ability to adhere to the insect's body wall or the external surface of the grains treated with them.

Jiang *et al.* (2015) mentioned that nanoparticles cause toxicity to insects they are treated with due to their penetration through the cuticle and entry into the cells. They bind with proteins, sulfur, or phosphorus in the DNA, causing disturbances in enzymes and muscles. This leads to disruptions in cell membranes, resulting in cellular dysfunction and eventual cell death. Nanoparticles also cause partial degradation of the epithelial cells in the midgut, leading to the formation of vacuoles in these cells and damaging their membranes. In many cases, it is difficult to determine whether the toxicity of nanoparticles (especially metallic ones) is due to

the material itself or the ions generated by it. It is believed that several types of nanoparticles pass through cell walls and then produce toxic ions that disrupt cell functions (Benelli, 2018). Habib (2022) found that silica oxide achieved the highest mortality rate of 100% in the second larval stage at concentrations of 100 and 200 mg kg⁻¹ compared to the fifth larval stage, where the mortality rate was 92.0% in larvae and 77.5% in adults at a concentration of 200 mg kg⁻¹ after 15 days of treating the wheat.

Ecotoxicological Assessment of Plant-Based Pesticides and Hydrophilic Nanosilica on the Mortality Rate of Rust Red Flour Beetles *T. castaneum*

The synergistic effect of the plant-based pesticide at a concentration of 2 ml liter⁻¹ with hydrophilic nanosilica at 0.2 g liter⁻¹ water (Table 4) demonstrated superior performance of Tundexir pesticide. It resulted in the highest mortality rates, reaching 100% after 7 days of treatment, with a rate of 84.16%, compared to Balazin pesticide, which achieved a mortality rate of 96.66% at a concentration of 77.50%.

Table 4. The Effect of Synergy Between Plant-Based Pesticide (2 ml) and Hydrophilic Nanosilica (0.2 g liter-1) on the Percentage of Mortality of *T. castaneum* Beetles

Treatments	The percentage of mortality after different treatment periods (Days)(				Mortality rate (%)
	1	3	5	7	
Balizin	63.33	70.00	83.33	96.66	77.50
Tundexir	66.66	76.66	90.00	100.00	84.16
Control	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mean time	44.44	47.77	57.77	65.55	
L.S.D. 0.05	Treatment = 3.97 Time = 4.58 Interaction= 7.94				

The insecticidal activity of nanostructured aluminum-based pesticides (NSA) as seed coatings against three storage pests, *Oryzaephilus surinamensis*, *Stegobium paniceum*, and *T. confusum*, was evaluated. Application at a concentration of 400 mg kg⁻¹ resulted in 100% mortality for *S. paniceum*, followed by 80.64% for *O. surinamensis*, and 79.41% for *T. confusum* (Belhamel *et al.*, 2020). Several studies suggest the use of nanostructured compounds as coatings and

polymers to enhance the penetration and permeability of insecticides, thereby strengthening and activating their effectiveness. These compounds have been used in combination with insecticides such as Imidacloprid, Deltamethrin, Lambdacyhalothrin, and others (Mohammed & Alkazafy, 2014).

Conclusion

Plant-based insecticides such as Tandexir proved more effective, achieving mortality rates of 93.33% for Tandexir and 83.33% for Balizin after 5 days of treatment. The optimal dosage for both Tandexir and Balizin was 4 ml liter-1, resulting in 100% mortality after 7 days. Combining plant-based insecticides with a water-friendly nanosilica compound significantly increased efficacy against *Tribolium castaneum*. Nanosilica formulations at a dose of 0.4 g liter-1 demonstrated high mortality rates of 100%. after 7 days, highlighting their effectiveness.

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